

Polarographic Reduction of Monochloro-Pentammine Cobalt (III) Ion in Presence of Aminoacids

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Polarographic reduction of monochloro-pentammine cobalt (III) ion was carried out in strong sulphate medium in presence of various aminoacids which resulted in a positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ of the first reduction ($\text{Co}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$) wave of the complex. These shifts in E_1 values have been correlated with the substitution of aminoacids as a unidentate ligand in place of chlorine in the coordination sphere.

Monochloro-pentammine cobalt (III) chloride, $[\text{R Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ where $\text{R} = [\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5]$, gets aquated in water with the result that chlorine in the inner sphere is replaced by a water molecule^{1,2}. Glycine, α -alanine and their substituted products replace chlorine from this complex as a unidentate ligand through the carboxyl ion³⁻⁴. Unlike Willis *et al.*⁵, we have found that this compound like other cobaltamines gives two first step ($\text{Co}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$) irreversible reduction waves, (one of them being that of the aquated product) in all supporting electrolytes except in strong sulphate solution (0.5 M). In the presence of the latter, only one well defined reversible wave with an $E_1 = -0.456 \text{ V}$ (*vs sce*) was obtained.

In presence of excess of sulphate ions, the aquation is checked and the above chloride forms a complex⁶ with sulphate ion in the inner sphere $(\text{R SO}_4)\text{Cl}$, A. Now if in the compound A, a strongly coordinating group like aminoacid is introduced, it will replace chlorine or water or sulphate from the coordination sphere. Such a substitution should create a larger asymmetry of the ligand field in the complex, resulting in a more positive shift in E_1 values of the complex. This view point was verified by substituting a number of aminoacids including glycine and α -alanine in A.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monochloro-pentammine cobalt (III) chloride was prepared by the method of Hynes *et al.*⁷ using A.R. cobalt chloride. Aminoacids were all of reagent grade BDH or S. Merck products. Lysine and arginine were used as their hydrochlorides. Potassium sulphate used was S. Merck Proanalysis grade. Solutions were prepared in air-free double-distilled water and 0.005% methyl red was used as maxima suppressor.

A Heyrovsky Polarograph model LP 55A was operated manually with a PYE Scalamp galvanometer in the external circuit. The polarographic cell was immersed in a water thermostat maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified hydrogen was used for deaeration of the solutions. Solutions were allowed to stand for 24 hrs before recording their polarograms.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Addition of glycine, α -alanine, dl-valine, l-lysine, l-arginine, l-leucine, l- and dl-threonines and dl-serine to A results in the formation of aminoacid substituted complexes which do not undergo hydrolytic decomposition even on heating over water bath for several hours.

Monochloro-pentammine cobalt (III) ion is reduced reversibly with single electron transfer (confirmed by logarithmic analysis method) at the dme with $E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.456$ V (*vs sce*) in 0.5 M potassium sulphate solution (Fig. 1, curve 1). Effect of mercury height on the

Fig. 1. curves 1-6.— 1.0×10^{-3} M of A in presence of dl-valine (0.0 to 1.0×10^{-1} M)
curves 7-11.— 1.0×10^{-3} M of A in presence of dl-serine (0.2 to 1.0×10^{-1} M)
All the curves start at 0.0 potential.

diffusion current shows that the wave is diffusion controlled. The addition of a number of aminoacids resulted in a positive shift in the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of the above wave. The results are summarized in Table 1, and typical curves in the case of dl-valine and dl-serine are shown

TABLE 1

Variation in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ with different amounts of aminoacids

Sl. No.	Aminoacid	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ V (<i>vs sce</i>) in the corresponding complexes Aminoacid concentration $\times 10^2$ M in parenthesis.					
1.	α -alanine	-0.430 (1)	-0.420 (2)	-0.410 (3)	-0.400 (4)	-0.395 (5)	-0.390 (6)
2.	glycine	-0.400 (2)	-0.380 (4)	-0.370 (6)	-0.360 (8)	-0.355 (10)	
3.	dl-valine	-0.390 (2)	-0.380 (4)	-0.360 (6)	-0.355 (8)	-0.345 (10)	—
4.	l-lysine	-0.410 (1)	-0.385 (2)	-0.375 (3)	-0.370 (4)	-0.360 (5)	-0.350 (6)
5.	l-arginine	-0.405 (1)	-0.385 (2)	-0.380 (3)	-0.370 (4)	-0.355 (5)	-0.340 (6)
6.	l-leucine	-0.400 (1)	-0.370 (2)	-0.365 (3)	-0.360 (4)	-0.350 (5)	-0.345 (6)
7.	l-threonine	-0.390 (1)	-0.365 (2)	-0.355 (3)	-0.345 (4)	-0.335 (5)	-0.330 (6)
8.	dl-serine	-0.365 (2)	-0.335 (4)	-0.320 (6)	-0.315 (8)	-0.305 (10)	—
9.	dl-threonine	-0.380 (1)	-0.360 (2)	-0.340 (3)	-0.330 (4)	-0.325 (5)	-0.315 (6)

in Figure 1 (curves 2-11). The second reduction wave of A, which is a two electron transfer one ($\text{Co}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\circ}$) is totally irreversible ($E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -1.25 \text{ V vs sce}$) and has been neglected in our studies.

Substitution reactions in cobalt pentammines accompanied by positive shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been reported by Vlcek^{8,9} where it has been reported that the positive shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ became more pronounced with the introduction of larger asymmetry in the coordination sphere¹⁰. Lengthening of the side chain or increase in the distance between the amino and the carboxyl group should result in larger shifts in the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of A.

The addition of very simple aminoacids like glycine and α -alanine introduces a little asymmetry in the electric field of the complex and this results in a very small shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of A. With dl-valine as the lengthening and branching of the side chain occurs, the extent of asymmetry caused is increased which causes larger shifts as compared to glycine and α -alanine.

Structural considerations reveal that lysine and arginine, with a distant NH_2 group and guanidine group respectively in their molecules, should introduce still large asymmetry and hence a larger shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values. However, the addition of dl-serine, l- and dl-threonines produces maximum shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ which may be due to the presence of strongly electro-negative hydroxyl group in them which disturbs the symmetry of the complex to a maximum.

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